

How do cross-ecosystem interactions affect Nantucket salt marsh food web structure and ecosystem functioning?

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Abstract

New England salt marshes are some of the most productive and important coastal ecosystems but they are currently under threat from human activities in adjacent terrestrial and marine habitats (e.g. eutrophication from terrestrial runoff and the removal of top predators). Recent experiments indicate that predators are likely key interactors along salt marsh creek banks but the identity and relative importance of common cross ecosystem predators are unknown and likely vary from marsh to marsh. Surveys in 2014 indicate that salt marshes of Nantucket host a diverse suite of predators including marine (e.g. green crabs, blue crabs, American eels, mummichogs) and terrestrial species, (e.g. shorebird predators such as Great Egrets, gulls, American Oystercatchers, Greater Yellowlegs, Willets, and Whimbrels). I used a combination of surveys, tethering experiments, and a manipulative field experiment to answer the following questions: (1) What are the most common predators of creek bank invertebrates in Nantucket salt marshes? and (2) What is the relative importance of shorebird and marine predators on the community structure and ecosystem functioning of Nantucket marshes? Preliminary results indicate that marine predators such as green crabs and blue crabs are likely keystone predators of marsh crabs, whereas bird predation is periodic. Marine predators have the largest affect on the marsh community, decreasing crab, mussel, and juvenile snail abundances. These same predators, likely green crabs and blue crabs and eels, also increase *Spartina* primary production. Determining the frequency and importance of cross ecosystem predators on creek bank processes will help understand how Nantucket salt marshes function and provision ecosystem services like erosion protection and nursery habitat availability.

Introduction and Background

Marshes are currently under threat from human activities in adjacent terrestrial and marine habitats due to eutrophication from terrestrial runoff and the removal of top predators (Deegan et al. 2007, Altieri et al. 2012). At the same time, salt marsh grasses provide complex foraging and refuge habitat for a high diversity of organisms from these bordering marine and terrestrial habitats (Kneib 1997, Bertness 1998, Wason and Pennings 2008) and interactions involving these species have important implications for overall marsh processes and species diversity. For example, in Cape Cod salt marshes, overfishing has reduced the number of marine predators, such as striped bass and cod, causing population densities of the herbivorous purple marsh crab, *Sesarma reticulatum*, to increase across its natural range. Increased above and below-ground *S. reticulatum* grazing from these dense populations has caused massive die-off of the foundation species *Spartina alterniflora* and subsequent creek bank erosion (Holdredge et al. 2009, Coverdale et al. 2012). Recent experiments indicate that the exclusion of predators increases *S. reticulatum* grazing and subsequent erosion of marsh creek banks in Cape Cod (Altieri et al. 2012), but the specific predators that are responsible for reducing crab densities are unknown and likely vary from marsh to marsh.

Despite a resident population of *S. reticulatum*, Nantucket marshes have not shown signs of creek bank erosion due to overgrazing although some banks have high numbers of crab burrows. Observations last summer indicated that crab damage was present along banks, but was not widespread throughout marshes. Based on these observations I hypothesized that the unique, diverse assemblage of marine and avian marsh predators may be protecting Nantucket marsh creek banks by keeping *S. reticulatum* densities below an overgrazing threshold. I used a combination of surveys, tethering experiments, and a manipulative field experiment to answer the following questions: (1) **What are the most common predators of creek bank invertebrates in Nantucket salt marshes?** and (2) **What is the relative importance of shorebird and marine predators on the community structure and ecosystem functioning of Nantucket marshes?**

Methods

Predator surveys

To identify the common predators in Nantucket salt marshes, NCF and I collected intensive food web data at three marshes on Nantucket: Medouie Creek, Folgers Marsh, and Eel Point. To determine the abundance and identity of avian predators in these marshes, I conducted 3, 10 minute bird surveys in three locations within each marsh, measuring species, activity (flying, standing in marsh, standing in creek, hunting), and its location (upland edge, creekbank, mudflat, in creek). For each of the three observation points, there will be 30 total minutes of observation time within each zone. To determine the identity of marine predators in Nantucket marshes I deployed unbaited fish and crab traps ($n = 10$) during day and night high tides along creek banks at each site. These traps were checked each day, recording species and size of any fish or crabs that were caught.

To determine frequency of predation and identity of predators in Nantucket marshes, I conducted video-monitored tether surveys using adult purple marsh crabs (*S. reticulatum*), the fiddler crab *Uca pugnax*, juvenile ribbed mussels *Geukensia demissa* (3 cm shell height), and amphipods (*Orchestria sp.*) along creek banks in Folgers Marsh. Tethered individuals were placed either on the marsh creek bank or 2 m behind the bank on the marsh platform. To determine the identity of predators that attack tethered animals, I used GoPro cameras as the tide came up at each marsh site to observe underwater interactions. Using monofilament fishing line and marine ZSpar epoxy, crabs will be allowed to move around the sediment but will not be given access to burrows for 24 hours (two high tides). From this footage, I calculated frequency of predation events and the identity of all successful or unsuccessful predation attempts. Nantucket data was compared with tethering studies from other marshes in Massachusetts (Plum Island, Waquoit Bay)

Field Experiment

To determine the separate and combined effects of marine and avian predators in Nantucket marshes, I set up a fully factorial bird by marine predator exclusion experiment in Folgers Marsh. I marked 20 $2 \times 2 \text{ m}^2$ identical plots of marsh along the main creek bank and each of these plots will be randomly assigned one of the following treatments ($n=5$): (1) All predator access, (2) Only marine predator access, (3) Only avian predator access, (4) No predator access. Treatment 2, only marine predator access, was constructed by tying multiple horizontal rows of monofilament fishing line around four, 1m tall PVC poles. Treatment 3, only avian predator access, was a 'high tide cage' made of knotted seine netting (Memphis Net and Twine) and floats. The nets fit around PVC poles on the corners of the plot and raised on each incoming high tide by floats connected to the top of the nets. This process was repeated for every high tide that would flood the plot. Video data indicates that nearly 100% of fish and crabs were excluded. Treatment 4, no predator access, was a combination of treatment 2 and 3. To simulate a natural creek bank community, each plot was populated with natural densities of the most common creek bank invertebrates (8 fiddler crabs *Uca pugnax*, 4 *Sesarma reticulatum*, and 60 ribbed mussels *Geukensia demissa*) and initial *Spartina alterniflora* stem density was recorded for each plot.

To determine how the marsh community changed throughout the course of the experiment, I recorded monthly community structure. Specifically I measured stem density of *S. alterniflora* and percent cover of all algal species. To describe the animal community present in each plot, I recorded density of mussels (*Geukensia demissa*), snails (*Littoraria littorea*), and crab burrows (both *Uca sp* and *Sesarma reticulatum*). To determine the effect of predator removals on the simultaneous performance of multiple ecosystem functions, I measured the following ecosystem functions: *S. alterniflora* net primary production (NPP), *Spartina* decomposition rate, sedimentation rate and recruitment rate. To measure *Spartina* NPP I calculated the change in live biomass over the experiment. To quantify decomposition rate, I measured the mass loss of dead *Spartina* stems in each plot, monthly. To quantify sedimentation rate, I placed small petri dish sediment traps in each plot, and measured the mass of sediment deposited in each plot over the course of a week. To measure recruitment rate, I placed Tupperware containers with a Tuffy sponge fastened in into each of my plots. This recruitment trap provided

habitat for recruits to settle. I collected these once a month and replaced them after recording any worms, crabs, snails, or other organisms that settled.

Results (NOTE: this is initial data. Complete data is still being processed and analyzed!)

Predator surveys

I am still processing data from the predator surveys but initial observations from baited crab traps indicate that the most common creek bank predators are green crabs (*Carcina maenas*) and blue crabs (*Callinectes sapidus*). GoPros and fish traps revealed the most common fish predators as eels (*Anguilla anguilla*) as well as many omnivorous fish such as mummichogs (*Fundulus heteroclitus*), and killfish (*F. confluentus*, *F. majalis*). Bird survey data are also being processed. The most common bird predators along creek banks were Great and Snowy Egrets, Blue and Night Herons, Oystercatchers, Gulls, Whimbrels, Willets, and Canadian geese. The survey data collected will be combined with eBird data to build a full avian predator food web for Nantucket marshes

Tethering experiments along the Massachusetts coast showed that predation on tethered individuals is higher on marsh creek banks than on the marsh platform at all sites (Figure 1). Predation rates in Nantucket were comparable to other Southern New England sites along the creek bank but were much lower in the marsh platform, likely because of the low tidal amplitude. Notably, *Sesarma* were preyed upon within one tidal cycle in Folgers Marsh, the fastest in New England

Effect of Bird and Marine Predators on Community Structure

Data collected and analyzed from the four month field experiment suggests that marine predators have a stronger affect on the community structure of salt marsh creek banks (Table 1). Fiddler crab density (80.8 burrows/m²), *Sesarma reticulatum* density (3.2 burrows/m²), ribbed mussel density (43.6 mussels/m²) and juvenile snail density (24 juvenile *Littorina littorea*/m²) were all the highest in plots where no predators were allowed (TABLE 1). Marine predators decreased the density of fiddler crab burrows, *Sesarma* burrows, and juvenile snail abundances. Bird predators only slightly decreased fiddler crab burrows and had no effect on the other community metrics. Bird and marine predators synergistically decreased fiddler crab burrows more than just one predator species alone, but did not have any other combined effects on the marsh community.

Effect of Bird and Marine Predators on Ecosystem Function

Early results from the predator exclusion experiment show that predators did not change recruitment or decomposition rates (Figure 2). However, predators in general increased live *Spartina* stem density over the course of the experiment (Figure 2) and other biomass data (not reported) indicates that this trend will hold. Predators also reduced the total number of *Sesarma* grazed stems throughout the experiment, suggesting that this top down control is responsible for the differences in plant mass

Discussion

Initial results from this study indicate that predators, specifically marine predators, increase *Spartina alterniflora* primary production over the course of a growing season. This trophic cascade has been hypothesized (Altieri et al. 2012) but the species responsible for this effect had not been identified. These results, combined with GoPro data, indicates that blue and green crabs specifically are responsible for the regulation of creek bank productivity. I found little evidence that bird predators affect any of the measured community dynamics, but they did reduce the number of fiddler crabs in each plot. Marine predators, on the other hand, reduced *Sesarma*, fiddler crab, and mussel densities. Juvenile snails also had higher survival rates where marine predators were excluded.

High variation in the effects of birds is likely due to the scale of the experiment. Although each plot was large (2 x 1 m), this might not have been large enough to capture the foraging range of important bird predators. It is important to note though that medium to small birds were often observed in and around plots that were not excluding them. The most common birds were medium sized predators like plovers, whimbrels, and willets. These birds are known to feed on fiddler crabs when available, and could likely be responsible for decreased fiddler crab burrows in bird only plots.

The early results of this study indicate that predator identity is key in the regulation of salt marsh community structure and ecosystem processes. Although most ecosystem function data has yet to be processed, I already know that predators had an affect on net primary production and recruitment rates. Sedimentation rates, decomposition rates, and soil respiration data is forthcoming.

This research will represent an important contribution to the salt marsh community ecology literature, as well as solve a big unknown in New England salt marshes: what predators can help prevent erosion of creek banks from crab burrowing. Additionally this will help understand the context-dependency of cross-ecosystem interactions and how predator identity can affect community structure and ecosystem functioning.

Literature cited

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Predators present	Fiddler crab density (burrows/m ²)	SE	Sesarma density (burrows/m ²)	SE	Mussel density (individuals/m ²)	SE	Juvenile L. littorina density (individuals/m ²)	SE
none	80.8	11.2	3.2	0.8	43.6	4.3	24.0	7.0
Marine only	37.6	7.2	0.8	0.8	24.8	7.2	0.8	0.8
Bird only	51.2	20.4	2.4	1.0	48.4	14.3	7.2	3.2
all	20.0	4.0	0.8	0.8	14.0	3.5	2.4	1.0

Table 1. Effect of bird or marine predators on salt marsh creek bank community including (a) fiddler crab burrow densities, (b) ribbed mussel density, (c) snail density, and (d) *Sesarma* burrow density

Table 2. Mean number and identity of birds found along Folgers Marsh creek banks over three sampling days in August 2015

Bird species	Mean no. birds/sampling event
Wimbrell	15.3
Willet	12.2
Yellow legs	24.1
Semipalmated plover	11.8
Piping plover	10
Herring gull	3.9
Black backed gull	0.3
Saltmarsh sparrow	6.1
Canada goose	8
Barn swallow	32.2
Tree swallow	26.4
Great egret	2.4
Snowy egret	9.2
American oystercatcher	3.9

Figure 1. Mortality rate (number of individuals dead/day) for tethered (a) fiddler crabs, (b) mussels, (c) *Sesarma reticulatum* purple marsh crabs, and (d) amphipods at Folgers Creek Marsh, as well as other marshes in New England for comparison

Figure 2. Effect of bird and marine predators on various measures of ecosystem functioning. Treatments on the x axis indicate which predators were allowed in each plot. Predators had minimal effect on the number of recruits found in traps (top left), and decomposition rate (top right). However, excluding marine predators had a non-significant effect on live *Spartina* density (bottom left) which I expect to change when final biomass data is processed. Predators had a strong effect on the number of stems grazed by *Sesarma* (bottom right) by reducing grazing in all instances